

**THE HISTORY OF THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE AND THE STAGES
OF ITS DEVELOPMENT UNTIL TODAY.**

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Abstract: Almost all modern languages have an original language. This early language with all its derivatives forms a language "family". English belongs to the group of Indo-European languages. It also includes French, Italian, German, Norwegian and Greek. This article contains information about the emergence and at the same time the stages of development of the English language, in which period it was used by which peoples.

Key words: Language families, Anglo-Saxon tribes, dialects, modern English, great migration, runic texts.

Changes in language are to understand the speech activity of the people and to know that it is related to different aspects of life. At the same time, it should be taken into account that this relationship is very complex and ambiguous, and that language is manifested in different situations. Also, it should be recognized that the development process of language development is not uniform and determining the development strength of this process is not easy in all cases. For example, the development of the vocabulary is easier than the phonetic system. The phonetic system has more difficult problems. There are still enough unsolved issues in this area. It is known that language changes happen slowly. A person does not notice the progress of this process. In particular, if we look at the changes in the English language system, it has taken different forms in different periods. In some historical periods, the pace of change in the English language has accelerated, and in others it has slowed down. Based on this, it can be concluded that in order to know the language, it is necessary to know its history and the historical processes connected with the development of the language. The history of the English language is the dialect of one of the Germanic tribes spoken by the inhabitants of Britain in the 5th century, and the process of becoming a language spoken by more than 2 billion people around the world in one and a half thousand years. English is a West Germanic language, based on Anglo-Frisian dialects brought to Britain in the 5th-7th centuries BC by Germanic invaders and settlers from present-day North-West Germany, West Denmark and the Netherlands. English is a language belonging to the Germanic group of the Indo-European family. The language of the English people.

Official language of Australia, USA, United Kingdom, India, Ireland, South Africa, Canada, Liberia, Malta and New Zealand. English is the 3rd most spoken language in the world (after Spanish and Mandarin Chinese). The main language of the European Union. During the Anglo-Saxon period, Old English became Middle English, which was spoken from the Norman Conquest until the end of the 15th century. The formation of the English language was significantly influenced by contacts with the North Germanic languages spoken by the Scandinavians who invaded and colonized Britain in the 8th to 9th centuries; this contact has led to many lexical borrowings and grammatical simplifications. The language was influenced by the conquests of the Normans, who spoke Old Norman, which became Anglo-Norman in English. Many Norman and French borrowings are included in the ecclesiastical and judicial vocabulary. The spelling system established during the Middle English period is still used today. Old English (VII-XI centuries) was called Anglo-Saxon and had 4 dialects: Northumbrian, Mercian, Wessex and Kentish. Literary English was formed on the basis of the Wessex dialect in the 9th-11th centuries. This family of dialects was brought to the east coast of Great Britain by the Germanic tribes, the Anglo-Saxons. The word English comes from the word Angles, and the ancestral land of this people was Angeln, which is now Schleswig-Holstein. Many English words are derived from Latin, although Latin was the language of the Christian Church and European thought. After the Viking invasions in the 8th and 9th centuries, English absorbed some of the Old Norse language. The conquest of England by the Normans in the 11th century led to the mixing of Norman French with English. It is for this reason that the English language is lexically and orthographically related to the Romance languages. As a result of the reduction of unstressed vowels in the Middle English language (12th-15th centuries), verb combinations underwent many changes. A new English language emerged in the 16th and 17th centuries. With the strong development of Great Britain between the 17th and 20th centuries and the secular influence of the United States in the 20th century, the international influence of English increased. English now has its own regional dialects. Scottish dialect in Great Britain; northern, southern, and central dialect groups, in the US there are Eastern, Mid-Atlantic (central), southern, eastern, middle, western dialect groups. The phonetic system of the English language has its own vowels and consonants. English is distinguished from other Germanic languages by the analytic construction mark. Auxiliary words (articles, auxiliary verbs, prepositions) and word order are of

great importance in expressing grammatical relations. English has borrowed about 70% of its words from other languages (Latin, French, Italian, Spanish, etc.). The difference between the American version of English and the British version can be explained by the fact that the first immigrants to North America (1607) came from London and its surroundings, and later came from Northern Britain and Ireland.

Early Modern English—Shakespearean—has been around since about 1500. It features many borrowings from Renaissance Latin and Ancient Greek, as well as borrowings from other European languages, including French, German, and Dutch. Pronunciation changes during this period included the "Great Vowel Shift" (phonetic changes in English during the 14th and 15th centuries), which affected the characteristics of long vowels. Modern English, which is still spoken today, has been used since the end of the 17th century. Since British colonization, English has spread widely in Great Britain, Ireland, USA, Canada, Australia, New Zealand, India, parts of Africa and other countries. Currently, it is a means of international communication. Old English included a variety of dialect groups, reflecting the origins of the Anglo-Saxon kingdoms established in different parts of Great Britain. As a result, the West Saxon dialect of the language became dominant. Old English greatly influenced Middle English. One type of English is Scottish. It is traditionally spoken in parts of Scotland and Northern Ireland. Sometimes it is considered as an independent language. English has its roots in the languages of the Germanic peoples of Northern Europe. During the Roman Empire, most German settlements remained independent of Rome, although some southwestern regions were part of the empire. Some Germans served in the Roman army. Troops from Germanic tribes such as Tungras, Batavas and Frisians served in Britain under Roman rule. With the fall of the Western Roman Empire, German settlements expanded during the Great Migration. The languages originally spoken by the Germanic peoples of Great Britain were part of the West Germanic branch of the Germanic language family. They consisted of dialects of the Ingeveon language group (named after a large group of Ingeveon Germanic tribes) spoken by the Nordic peoples of modern Denmark, northwestern Germany, and the Netherlands. Due to some similarities between the Old English and Old Russian languages, this group was called Anglo-Frisian languages. Around 800 BC, representatives of the Indo-Europeans, the Celts, moved from the mainland to Britain. The people who lived before them in this area left no trace of the English language. In 55-54 BC, the Romans appeared in Britain. Gaius Julius Caesar

conducted two campaigns here. In 44 BC, Britain was declared a province of the Roman Empire. Emperors Claudius, Hadrian, Septimius Severus visited the island. By order of Emperor Honorius, Britain ceased to be a Roman province. In 449, the Germanic tribes of England, Saxons, Jutes and Frisians entered Great Britain. Anglo-Saxon began to displace Celtic from everyday use. In modern English, the names of English settlements and bodies of water return to English. For example, Avon (Avon is "River" in Celtic). From the dialects of the German settlers was created the language that would later be called Anglo-Saxon, which is now often called Old English. This language brought Celtic and Latin from Roman Britain, most of the territories of Great Britain, which later entered the Kingdom of England, and the Celtic languages preserved in the territories of Scotland, Wales and Cornwall. Through the Germans, English received several Latin words: "wine" — Lat. wine nok "pear" - lat. Pirum; "pepper" - lat. piper.

Conclusion: The study of the history of the language provides a deep understanding of the modern English language, its connection with various factors, the result of a complex process of development, and its place among other languages. At the same time, the history of the English language can be used as an auxiliary subject in the study of the history of England and English literature. The goals and objectives of the course in the history of the English language are not only to present facts, but also to determine the laws of language development.

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